

Fingerprinting changes of source apportionments from mixed land uses in stream sediments before and after an exceptional rainstorm event

I. Lizaga¹, L. Gaspar¹, W. Blake², B. Latorre¹, A. Navas¹

¹ Department of Soil and Water. Estación Experimental de Aula-Dei, Spanish National Research Council (EEAD-CSIC), Spain. Avenida Montañana, 1005, 50059 Zaragoza (Spain).

² School of Geography, Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Plymouth, UK

- ilizaga@eead.csic.es; +34 670306713/+34 976716143
- anavas@eead.csic.es

ABSTRACT

The loss of fertile topsoil is one of the principal soil degradation problems in mountain agroecosystems worldwide. Soil erosion rates reach their maximum during exceptional storm events that remove soil particles, especially from unprotected topsoil. In Mediterranean mountainous environments, several centuries of non-irrigated agriculture and the subsequent removal of natural vegetation for developing agriculture has increased the surface area prone to erosion. In addition, the irregularity in exceptional precipitation events results in a great loss of fertile soil, the subsequent siltation of reservoirs and a decrease in water quality. To analyse the soil response to exceptional events, 161 source samples were collected in a 23 km² catchment that was mostly cultivated at the beginning of the last century. Source samples were distributed over the five main land use/land covers such as agricultural land, pine afforestation, open forest, bare soil and channel bank areas. Furthermore, 20 channel bed sediment samples were collected along the main streams before and after the exceptional storm event to document

27 changes in the sediments. In addition, floodplain sediments were collected to provide a
28 close replication of sediments deposited during regular storm events. Source
29 apportionments were calculated using the FingerPro mixing model in the pre-event,
30 regular events and post-event scenarios.

31 The unmixing outputs displayed a large variation of source apportionments from
32 the upper part to the lower part of the catchment and from pre- to post-event sediments.
33 After the event, a decrease of more than 70% of the clay fraction and its associated
34 elements such as Fe, Al, K, Ba, Sr, Rb, Pb, Zn, V, ^{137}Cs , ^{40}K , ^{232}Th and SOC along with
35 a rise in contents of elements associated with the coarse fraction (Si, Nb, Zr, Ti, P and
36 ^{226}Ra) was recorded in the channel bed sediments. At the catchment outlet, the pre-event
37 sediment showed substantial contributions from bare soil (29%) and from agriculture and
38 channel banks, which both reached 35%, while the channel bank was the main source
39 along the catchment ranging between 44 and 71%. The low contribution from soil under
40 natural covers with a mean value less than 4% underlines the benefits of vegetation to
41 prevent soil loss. In the post-event sediment, the channel bank contribution increased up
42 to 63% at the catchment outlet. Our findings highlight the hazards of exceptional storm
43 events on modifying sediment source contribution and exporting fine sediment.

44

45 **1. Introduction**

46 The impact of soil erosion on mountain agroecosystems has received increasing
47 attention due to the vulnerability of shallow soil to erosion processes, which are the main
48 cause of soil loss and subsequent land degradation. Very intense rainstorms after dry
49 periods are relatively frequent in the Mediterranean region ([Serrano-Notivoli et al., 2017](#)).
50 Mediterranean agroecosystems are susceptible to degradation due to irregular space-time
51 distribution of high-intensity rainfall and storm events, followed by long dry periods

52 (Mariani and Parisi, 2014). The importance of these exceptional rainstorms has been
53 highlighted, and they have been found to be responsible for major geomorphological
54 changes including piping, gully formation, landslides and subsequent soil loss (Grodek et
55 al., 2012; Nadal-Romero et al., 2013). Thus, fragile soils with low nutrient contents
56 existing in Mediterranean mountain agroecosystems, along with an absence of dense
57 vegetation cover due to deforestation in the past century, have created areas prone to
58 erosion (Navas et al., 2017). Soils without vegetation cover are easily erodible during
59 exceptional storm events such as the three-day long exceptional rainstorm event that
60 occurred in 2012 in northeastern Spain (Serrano-Muela et al., 2015).

61 Exceptional rainfall events accelerate soil and bedrock erosion on hillslopes,
62 which commonly results in higher sediment mobilisation and variations in sediment
63 sources released into the streams. Exported fine sediment produces an important indirect
64 impact such as rapid siltation of downstream water bodies that reached a maximum in the
65 Mediterranean mountains due to land abandonment in the mid-1950s (Navas et al., 2009).
66 Since the 1950s, Mediterranean mountain agroecosystems were commercialised through
67 technological progress and the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), which favoured
68 the expansion of certain management systems focused on more fertile and accessible land.
69 These practices produced a decline in traditional farming methods and converted
70 mountain agriculture into marginal agricultural land leading to the abandonment of the
71 countryside (Lasanta et al., 2016; Quijano et al., 2016a; Borrelli et al., 2017). Subsequent
72 natural vegetation regrowth (Navas et al., 2008) and afforestation during the 1960s and
73 1980s produced a large effect on reducing slope-channel coupling and runoff due to an
74 increase in plant cover (Cavalli et al., 2013; Heckmann et al., 2018; Llana et al., 2019).
75 Thus, Mediterranean agricultural soils suffered significant modifications due to land use/
76 land cover changes (Romanya and Rovira, 2011). As a consequence of such changes,

77 cultivated Mediterranean fields show large variability in soil losses with average soil
78 redistribution rates between -30 to 15 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, while in other land uses that offer
79 protection to the soil surface (such as open forest), rates are much more moderate, varying
80 from -3 to 5 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Navas et al., 2014; Lizaga et al., 2018a).

81 Currently, soil erosion is an estimated 10–40 times greater than soil formation
82 rates (Pimentel, 2006; Verheijen et al., 2009). Various approaches have been suggested
83 for sediment yield monitoring and quantification of soil redistribution rates (Favis-
84 Mortlock et al., 2008; Walling and Collins, 2008; Dutta, 2016; Wynants et al., 2018).
85 However, erosion processes are mostly influenced by a variety of driving forces such as
86 slope, land management, altitude, vegetation cover, land use, soil type and changing
87 weather patterns and extremes under current climate (Renard et al., 2011; Lana-Renault
88 et al., 2013; Lecce et al., 2013; Buendia et al., 2016; Nadal-Romero et al., 2019; Shang et
89 al., 2019). Thus, to control soil erosion, it is important to recognise the most susceptible
90 areas, soils or land uses exposed to erosion processes as these processes lead to the loss
91 of soil nutrients.

92 Concerns about the nutrient loss associated with fine particles due to soil erosion
93 have led to analysis methods for quantifying and predicting erosion rates of fine grain
94 sediment. To this purpose geochemistry, magnetic properties, radiotracers and modelling
95 approaches offer considerable potential for studying erosion processes and calculating
96 soil redistribution rates (Navas et al., 2005; Gaspar et al., 2013; Quijano et al., 2016b;
97 Masselink et al., 2017). In areas where rill erosion is dominant, studies at the slope scale
98 have proven effective (Li et al., 2009). However, few studies quantify soil redistribution
99 rates at catchment or river scale (Mabit et al., 2002; Porto et al., 2003; Navas et al., 2013;
100 Lizaga et al., 2018a; Chen et al., 2019).

101 Large-scale erosion after exceptional rainstorm events has occurred irregularly in
102 the northeastern part of the Spanish Peninsula (Gutiérrez et al., 1998; White et al., 1997;
103 García-Ruiz et al., 2002). Exceptional storm events and the subsequent overflow of river
104 banks typically increase sediment transfer and suspended sediment loads in river
105 catchments triggering variations in sediment solute concentrations (Winston and Criss,
106 2002).

107 The large increase in fine grain sediment mobilised during exceptional storm
108 events has been demonstrated to be one of the most widespread contaminants in aquatic
109 ecosystems, compromising water quality and causing reservoir siltation (Navas et al.,
110 2004). For these reasons, defining the sources of eroded fine-grained sediment is a
111 fundamental requirement for catchment management as well as for understanding the
112 evolution of landscapes and delineating the most sensitive areas to soil loss.

113 Determining sediment provenance in catchments using conventional monitoring
114 techniques is often challenging, but in most environments it can be undertaken by
115 applying sediment source fingerprinting methods. Due to the growing use of
116 fingerprinting methods, several unmixing models such as IsoSource (Phillips and Gregg,
117 2003), MixSIR (Moore and Semmens, 2008), SIFT (Pulley and Collins, 2018) and
118 FingerPro (Palazón et al., 2015a; Lizaga et al., 2018) have appeared over the last years
119 for pollution and ecological purposes. To date, there are several studies on identifying
120 source apportions by fingerprinting techniques (Klages and Hsieh, 1975; Walling et al.,
121 1979; Yu and Oldfield, 1989; Collins et al., 1996; Evrard et al., 2013; Schuller et al.,
122 2013; Palazón et al., 2015b; Meusburger et al., 2018; Upadhayay et al., 2018), but only a
123 few have quantified the sediment provenance after an exceptional rainstorm event
124 (Martínez-Carreras et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2017), and none of these studies have

125 compared whether there were changes in the provenance of sediment before and after an
126 exceptional storm event.

127 To evaluate the unstudied effect of this unstudied phenomenon, its source
128 apportionments were calculated using the new R package FingerPro mixing model (Lizaga et
129 al., 2018b) that was tested with artificial samples by Gaspar et al. (2019a). For this
130 purpose, we implemented the unmixing model in two different datasets, before and after
131 a three-day exceptional rainstorm event in a representative catchment of the Prepyrenean
132 region. The 2012 event corresponded to a return period of 142 yr calculated at the outlet
133 of the Yesa reservoir located 30 km north from the catchment (Serrano-Muela et al.,
134 2015). Our objectives are (i) to analyse whether sediment properties vary along the main
135 streams before and after the exceptional storm event, (ii) to quantify and trace the
136 sediment provenance before the 2012 exceptional rainstorm event in different parts of the
137 study catchment and (iii) to examine whether sediment source apportionments after the
138 exceptional storm event differed from the ones during normal discharge.

139 Therefore, our multi-approach combining spatiotemporal analysis of soil
140 properties and fingerprinting modelling is aimed to determine how an exceptional storm
141 event modifies the sediment properties of the streambed sediments and how contributions
142 from sediment sources might change. To this aim, our work represents a unique
143 opportunity to track the changes in sediment contribution associated with exceptional
144 storm events due to the availability of pre-event sediment and floodplain mixtures that
145 were resampled after the storm event. This paper sheds new light on the effect of heavy
146 storms in agriculture catchments and points out the most sensitive areas to these highly
147 erosive processes.

148

149 **2. Material and methods**

150 *2.1. The study area*

151 The study catchment (23 km²) is drained by an ephemeral stream tributary of the
152 Arba River located in Barué in the middle part of the Ebro Basin (Fig. 1). From the
153 geomorphological perspective, the catchment structure is dominated by the low angle dip
154 of the bedding and the presence of a Quaternary glacis located at the lower eastern part
155 of the catchment. The climate is characterised by cold winters and hot and dry summers.
156 The rainfall periods are concentrated in the spring and autumn seasons while the droughts
157 take place between these two humid periods. The area is subjected to very intense though
158 sometimes localised storms. The maximum and minimum annual temperatures are 30°C
159 and -6°C, respectively. The mean annual rainfall is about 500 mm.

160 At the start of the twentieth century, most of the catchment was agricultural land.
161 In the 1960s, nearly 60% of the catchment was croplands. However, during the next 10
162 yr, 75% of the agricultural land was abandoned. Currently, ~16% of the catchment is still
163 cultivated while open forest and pine occupy the remaining 83.5 % (Lizaga et al., 2017).
164 The main land use/land covers are agricultural, open forest and pine afforestation,
165 occupying 16%, 50% and 19% of the catchment area, respectively. In addition, most of
166 the agricultural land is located on a Quaternary glacis and on fluvial terraces with gentle
167 slopes occupying the valley floors. The upper part of the Quaternary glacis is dissected
168 by the La Reina tributary stream, an ephemeral stream with documented exceptional
169 discharges under heavy rainfalls. Rangelands occupy the highest altitudes and the
170 revegetated abandoned crops are mostly located at intermediate altitudes where most of
171 the abandoned crops were located in the past. Interspersed patches of highly disturbed
172 areas, including bare soil (subsoil), are dispersed all over the catchment, although it is
173 more abundant on the middle part on south-facing slopes. Valley floors are infilled by
174 eroded sediment from the slopes and are deeply incised by streams, especially from the

175 middle part of the catchment. The stream channel banks composed of loess type material
176 have steep talus that remains uncovered by vegetation. Thus, channel banks of these
177 upland agroecosystem catchments are characterised by deep straight walls due to flow
178 incision by high water energy released during heavy rainfalls.

179

180 *2.2. Soil sampling and analysis*

181 Potential sediment sources and sediment sampling locations were manually
182 identified during fieldwork campaigns in a design sampling scheme. Special attention
183 was paid to the connectivity index (Lizaga et al., 2017) and soil properties such as CaCO₃,
184 pH, EC, SOC, grain size, land use, soil classification (Lizaga et al., 2019) and soil
185 redistribution rates (Lizaga et al., 2018a).

186 A total of 161 source sediment samples were taken with a cylindrical core 5 cm
187 long and 6 cm in diameter, with four replicates at each sampling point combined in the
188 field to create a representative composite sample following the accepted methodology
189 proposed in fingerprinting studies (Owens et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2017).
190 Fingerprinting studies collect sediment source samples of variable depths, though 2 cm
191 depth is frequently used. However, heavy rainfall events in upland Mediterranean
192 agroecosystems produce deep rilling and can remove more than 2 cm of surface soil.
193 Thus, a 5 cm sample depth was selected in this study for the appropriate characterisation
194 of sediment eroded by exceptional rainfall events.

195 Samples were collected from cropland (AG), open forest (OF), pine afforestation
196 (PI), eroded subsoil (SS) and channel bank (CB). Source samples were distributed over
197 the land uses (AG, OF and PI) across the catchment using a 500 x 500 m grid to represent
198 the areal percentage of each land use. The sample points retained their grid location as
199 much as possible avoiding recent highly disturbed areas that could not be representative

200 of the sampling source. Furthermore, 14 subsoil samples were collected on eroded bare
201 soil distributed over the catchment, and another 18 samples were collected along the main
202 streams on the channel banks near the mixture samples (Fig. 1).

203 Two different types of sediment mixture samples were collected in the channel
204 bed along the main streams from the headwaters to the outlet of the catchment, before
205 and after the secondary tributary streams. Mixture sediment samples are: (i) 20 channel
206 bed samples collected before and after the 2012 storm event (identified as SMP 1–20),
207 and (ii) 8 floodplain sediment mixture collected at sampling points 2, 3, 6, 12, 14, 15, 17
208 and 20. Channel bed and floodplain sediment lie on top of sandstone outcrops and these
209 surface sediments can be easily washed away during heavy autumn rainfall events. Thus,
210 the aim of these different sampling methods was to provide a close replication of
211 sediments deposited before and after the exceptional discharge event and the sediment in
212 floodplains that corresponds to regular high discharge events (named as SFMP). Channel
213 bed sediments were taken with a cylindrical core 5 cm long and 6 cm in diameter with
214 three replicates at each sampling point. The same methodology was used for collecting
215 the sediment in floodplains.

216 The samples were air-dried, grinded, homogenised and sieved to ≤ 0.063 mm
217 following the most widespread methodology (Owens et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2017). In
218 addition, the selection of the ≤ 0.063 mm particle size for sources and mixtures was related
219 to the predominant silt texture of soils in the catchment (Table 1) and also because the
220 content of sand, silt and clay fractions were similar between source and mixture samples
221 (Table 1 and Fig. 2). Furthermore, the relationships between tracers and the size fractions
222 support that ≤ 0.063 mm fraction compiles the existing range of variation for most of the
223 study tracers. Particle size, stable elements, magnetic susceptibility and radionuclides
224 were analysed in the ≤ 0.063 mm fraction for all 161 sediment samples.

225 Grain size and magnetic susceptibility were analysed following the same
226 methodology as in Lizaga et al. (2019). The analyses of the stable elements were
227 performed at the Consolidated Radio-isotope Facility (CORIF, University of Plymouth)
228 by X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) using a Niton XL3T 950 He GOLDD+ XRF Analyser.
229 Samples were analysed for major and minor elements (Ba, Nb, Zr, Sr, Rb, Pb, Zn, Fe,
230 Mn, Cr, V, Ti, Ca, K, Al, Si, and Mg). Concentrations, obtained after three measurements
231 per element, are expressed in mg/kg.

232 Gamma emissions of ^{137}Cs , ^{226}Ra , ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K were analysed at the gamma
233 lab of the Experimental station of Aula-Dei (EEAD-CSIC) following the methodology
234 used in Lizaga et al. (2017) and Navas et al. (2018). The radionuclide activities are
235 expressed as massic activity in Bq kg^{-1} dry soil and counted for 43,200 s.

236

237 *2.3. Statistical analysis and sources selection*

238 The laboratory results were statistically analysed using R. A non-parametric
239 Kruskal Wallis test was used to evaluate whether sediment mixture properties varied
240 between the pre- and post-storm event (Fig. 2). Correlation plots (Fig. 3) were used to
241 evaluate the relationships and the differences between pre- and post-event soil properties.
242 Furthermore, to identify the relationships of the different sources in the selected sediment
243 mixtures, a Euclidian distance matrix with the normalised values and a cluster analysis
244 using the ward.D2 method was used with all the study properties (Fig. 4). As each mixture
245 point has different source samples, the subsequent clusters may vary from one point to
246 another and from headwater to lowlands.

247

248 *2.4. FingerPro mixing model and tracer selection*

249 The estimation of the relative contribution of each potential sediment source to
250 the pre- and post-event sediment mixtures and the statistical tests were done with the
251 FingerPro unmixing model and package.

252 Source apportionment solutions were defined by the mean and standard deviation
253 (SD) calculated from the results selected by the model. The SD of the selected solutions
254 and the density graph of the model helps to compare and evaluate the solution scattering
255 as large values indicate poor source contribution ascription.

256 A crucial requirement in fingerprint assessment is the implementation of previous
257 statistical tests to identify individual fingerprint properties, which discriminate between
258 potential sources to select the optimum set of fingerprint properties (Yu and Oldfield,
259 1989; Walling and Woodward, 1995; Collins et al., 1996; Collins et al., 1997; Palazón et
260 al., 2015a; Collins et al., 2017). Several studies following the methodology implemented
261 by Collins and Walling (2002) compare the range in the sources to the range in the
262 sediment mixture or target for each fingerprint property (Smith and Blake, 2014; Koiter
263 et al., 2018). The two-step statistical procedure proposed by Collins et al. (1997) and
264 Walling (2005) is included as an optional step in the FingerPro R package and was used
265 in this study. In addition, because of the type of sediment mixtures and its temporal
266 storage in the channel bed, P, SOC and grain size properties were considered non-
267 conservative, and they were excluded from the analysis following Koiter et al. (2013).

268 As the first step in tracer selection, the range test cannot definitively identify all
269 tracers that are behaving non-conservatively but it removes the tracers with the largest
270 differences with the mixture sample that could also reveal the existence of a non-sampled
271 source. As an intermediate step we used biplot charts as proposed by Pulley et al. (2015)
272 using the correlationPlot () function included in the FingerPro package to further check
273 the conservative behaviour of each pair of tracers. The second step suggested using the

274 KW test to remove those tracers that do not show significant differences between the
275 selected sources. The tracer selection should not be only based on statistical tests but also
276 in expert knowledge of the hydrological and geomorphological processes in the study
277 area. However, the use of many tests could remove a considerable number of tracers that
278 might restrict the discrimination between sediment sources (Blake et al., 2018). For this
279 reason, boxplot charts, LDA (Linear Discriminant Analysis) plots and correlation plots
280 are included in the FingerPro package to help in the decision. Three-step tracer selection
281 was implemented in this study: the range test and Kruskal-Wallis followed by the
282 inclusion or exclusion of some tracers based on ‘expert judgement’ informed by
283 visualising the tools included in the FingerPro package. None of the functions included
284 in the package are mandatory, and the tracer exclusions can be based on the charts and
285 results from the statistical tests.

286 To check the quality of FingerPro model, a set of virtual mixtures based on the
287 unmixing results and using the selected tracers at each sediment mixture point were
288 created. By unmixing the virtual mixtures versus the mean values of the sources for the
289 selected tracers it is possible to obtain for each mixture the RMSE values of the model.
290 Thus, by using virtual mixtures the results allow us to validate the model performance.

291

292 **3. Results**

293 *3.1. Temporal variation of soil properties along the streams*

294 The measured properties of the sediment mixtures collected in the pre- and post-
295 event campaigns are shown in Fig. 2. Mean clay content decreased from 12.7% to 7.6%
296 for pre- and post-event sediments, respectively. In pre-event sediment, SOC contents
297 were significantly higher (range: 0.46–3.31%) than in post-event sediment (range: 0.24–
298 1.8 %). Mean radionuclide activities decreased from pre- to post-event sediments for

299 ^{137}Cs (1.1–0.9 Bq kg⁻¹), ^{40}K (467.3–367.6 Bq kg⁻¹) and ^{232}Th (31.5–29.9 Bq kg⁻¹) but
300 increased for ^{226}Ra (26.0–30.3 Bq kg⁻¹), and ^{238}U (43.5–46.8 Bq kg⁻¹). Major element
301 contents varied in pre- and post-event sediment. Mean values were: Si (165,996–182,772
302 mg/kg), Al (35,231–32,370 mg/kg), Ca (174,207–171118 mg/kg), Mg (3320–3185
303 mg/kg), K (13,208–10,862 mg/kg), Ti (3036–3226 mg/kg), Fe (19,805–17214 mg/kg),
304 Mn (286–311 mg/kg) and P (987–1120 mg/kg).

305 A decrease of about 38% in fine fraction content in the post-event sediment was
306 coincidental with a decrease of stable elements and properties that were positively
307 correlated with clay fraction such as SOC, ^{137}Cs , ^{40}K , ^{232}Th , Ba, Sr, Rb, Pb, Zn, Fe, K, Al
308 and V (Figs. 2 and 3). On the contrary, the study properties with negative correlation with
309 clay but positively correlated with the coarse fraction, such as the magnetic properties
310 ^{226}Ra , Nb, Zr, Ti, P and Si, were enriched in the sediment after the storm event. ^{238}U , Mn,
311 Ca and carbonates were not correlated with any grain size fraction and did not show any
312 clear trend between pre- and post-event sediment. In general, there was an increase in the
313 intercorrelation between the study elements and properties that were correlated with grain
314 size fractions in post-event sediment (Fig. 3).

315 There were important variations when comparing the pre- and post-event study
316 properties between at the headwaters, the middle and lower part of the catchment. A
317 higher decrease in clay content (70%) was recorded in the middle part than in the
318 headwaters and lower part of the catchment, but the opposite was observed for sand,
319 which reached higher contents (59%) in the middle part of the catchment. Thus, most
320 properties positively correlated with clay showed similar decreasing trends in the
321 headwaters, middle and lower parts of the catchment.

322 The floodplain sediment as an intermediate stage between pre- and post- event
323 sediments showed a transitional variation in elements and properties. Thus, the clay

324 fraction in pre-event sediment decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in floodplains (17%), but
 325 the decrease reached as much as 42% in post-event sediment accompanied by a
 326 subsequent increase in sand fraction of 10% and 100% in floodplain and post-event
 327 sediment, respectively. Most of the properties such as ^{137}Cs , ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , Nb, Sr, Zr,
 328 Rb, Zn, Fe, K, Al, Ti, P, Si and V differed significantly between these stages and showed
 329 similar increasing or decreasing trends (Fig. 5). Furthermore, Ba, Cr, Ca, SOC and SOC
 330 fractions had similar values in pre-event and floodplain sediment with a sharp decrease
 331 in post-event sediment. However, ^{238}U , χ_{LF} , Pb, Mn and Ca did not show a clear trend
 332 between stages (Table 3).

333

334 3.2. Sources and tracers selection

335 The statistics of grain size, SOC and trace element properties for the potential
 336 sediment sources are presented in Table 1. The SOC contents were low, with a mean
 337 value of 2% and the SOC fractions ACF and SCF ranged from 0.3% to 5.9% and from
 338 0.036% to 1.38%, respectively. The low frequency (χ_{LF}) and frequency dependent (χ_{FD})
 339 mass magnetic susceptibility had a mean value of $46.64 \cdot 10^8 \text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$ and 7.31%,
 340 respectively. In AG, CB and SS sources, SOC contents were lower and significantly
 341 different from the other sources, with the highest values found in OF and PI. Furthermore,
 342 the means of ^{137}Cs , Ba, Sr and P in AG were significantly lower than those in the other
 343 land uses (OF, PI) ($p \leq 0.05$). Most properties in CB and SS significantly differed from the
 344 other sources except for radionuclides. Major elements such as Si, Al, Ca, Mg, K, Ti, Fe,
 345 Mn and P only had significant differences in SS compared to the other sources except for
 346 Fe and K, which had the lowest mean values in CB.

347 The LDA plot created with all the source samples showed overlapping between
 348 land use sources and illustrated low discrimination capacity for AG, OF and PI (Fig. 4).

349 The discrimination of sources that are not well characterised might reduce discrimination
350 or lead to erroneous model results. Thus, land uses were grouped in two different
351 combinations based on their spatial distribution in the catchment along with results from
352 a cluster analysis pursued with tracer data. In the lower part of the catchment, cluster
353 analysis showed the highest similarities between land uses with arboreal vegetation (OF
354 and PI) (Fig. 4). Furthermore, AG predominated in the lower part of the catchment and
355 had different mean values of ^{137}Cs , χLF , Ba, Zr, Fe, Mn, Ca, P and Sr than in OF and PI.
356 Thus, it was decided to merge both arboreal land uses in one source (OF+PI). On the other
357 hand, at the headwaters where PI dominates, AG and OF showed the highest similarities
358 in the analysed tracers (Fig. 4). In addition, the tracers selected by the statistical test in
359 each mixture point before and after grouping sources mostly coincide, supporting the
360 adopted merging. This methodology was implemented to homogenise the results and to
361 avoid including non-contributing or very low-contributing sources into our unmixing
362 model.

363 Following this approach and the different source points selected for each sediment
364 mixture, it was decided to create a set of optimum tracers for each mixture point. Table 2
365 shows the optimum set of tracers selected for unmixing sediment mixtures along the
366 stream for the pre- and post- event sediment mixtures and floodplain sediment. In
367 addition, the low RMSE values calculated when comparing the unmixing results for the
368 virtual mixtures with that of the channel bed and floodplain sediment mixtures validate
369 the results and the performance of the FingerPro model (Table 3).

370

371 *3.3. Sediment source contributions pre- and post- 2012 rainstorm event*

372 The average mean relative contributions of each potential source to the sediment
373 mixtures indicates that overall, CB was the predominant source both before and after the

374 event ranging between 35 ± 7 to $87\pm 13\%$, followed by SS with a mean contribution of
375 $24\pm 9\%$. On the other hand, AG contributed around $21\pm 9\%$ at the lower part of the
376 catchment but much less in the headwaters. In contrast, PI contributed around $10\pm 9\%$ at
377 the headwaters, but it was almost insignificant at the lower part of the catchment. The
378 sediment contribution supplied by OF+PI was only noticeable in the middle part of the
379 catchment at point 17 with a mean apportionment of $16\pm 6\%$ in the pre-event sediment.

380 Large variations in source contributions were recorded for each sediment mixture,
381 especially between sediment mixtures located at the headwaters and in the middle and
382 lower parts of the catchment (Fig. 1). Furthermore, sediment mixtures varied greatly
383 between the pre- and post- exceptional event.

384 In the headwaters, SS and CB were the main contributing sources. However,
385 following the cluster group and the significant apportionment (16% and 17%) of the
386 forests (OF+PI), it was decided to merge AG and OF (AG+OF) and separate the PI source.
387 The results for sediment mixture points (SMP) 13 and 15 showed a mean sediment supply
388 of 16% and 10% from the pine afforestation. The contribution from forests (OF+PI) was
389 not observed downstream from SMP 17. For the downstream sediment mixture points,
390 there were also significant differences between SMP 17 located in the central part of the
391 catchment and both SMP 18 and SMP 20 located downstream from the La Reina tributary
392 stream. The agricultural source contribution reached a maximum close to the outlet of the
393 catchment (SMP 18 and SMP 20) and decreased marginally in upstream sediment. On the
394 contrary, at SMP 17 the contribution of AG was negligible. However, the presence of
395 sediment from forests was detected with a mean contribution of up to 14%, being less
396 than 2% in SMP located downstream of SMP 17.

397 In the headwaters (SMP 13 and SMP 15) PI sediment was mostly washed out from the
398 streams in post-event sediment mixtures. SMP 13 showed a similar decrease in SS, thus

399 increasing CB contribution up to 80%. However, SS in SMP15 increased slightly with
400 the subsequent decrease in CB proportion. The middle part of the catchment also
401 experienced a sharp decrease in contributions from the different land uses. Moreover, the
402 SS apportionment in the middle part increased from 18% in the pre-event sediment to up
403 to 27% in the post-event sediment. A different history occurs downstream the La Reina
404 tributary stream at SMP 18 where agricultural apportionments increased largely while SS
405 and CB decreased. At the catchment outlet, a large increment in CB apportionment was
406 recorded along with a sharp decrease in SS and a small decrease of AG in the post-event
407 sediment. Furthermore, a slight increase from the forest source (OF+PI) was recorded.
408 The SS decrease recorded at the outlet of the catchment was supported by the results
409 extracted from the SFMP where 90% of the sediment contribution was supplied by CB
410 and AG. In addition, the unmixing results of the SFMP indicated an increase of PI and
411 SS sediment in regular high discharge events but the disappearance of PI sediment during
412 exceptional events. SFMP 17 revealed an increase in AG and a slight decrease in SS
413 sediment in the floodplain while it showed a sharp increase in SS with a total wash out of
414 AG sediment during the exceptional event. Besides that, at the catchment outlet SFMP
415 20 showed a decrease in AG and SS sediment but a progressive CB increase as seen in
416 Table 3.

417

418 **4. Discussion**

419 *4.1. Variation in soil properties due to the exceptional event*

420 Compared with the other sources, the significant differences in most properties
421 found in SS (except for the radionuclides) are because SS is composed of very degraded
422 soils that expose the substrate. In addition, SS is mostly located in areas with high
423 hydrological connectivity, likely increasing its delivery to streams during storm events.

424 In the talus of the streams, CB sediment consisting of loess type materials infilling the
425 valley floor is the nearest available source to be deposited in the channel. As such, SS and
426 CB are the most distinctive sources from the others. However, Fig. 4 shows some
427 similarities between CB and AG sources likely because the agricultural land is mostly
428 located on the valley floor on alluvial materials infilling the valleys that comprise the CB
429 source.

430 The significant differences in mean contents of SOC, ^{137}Cs , Ba, Sr and P in
431 agricultural land compared with PI and OF suggest that land use is one of the principal
432 factors affecting the variation in soil properties after five decades of land abandonment
433 as found by [Lizaga et al. \(2019\)](#). In addition, the scarce vegetation cover and the presence
434 of more degraded soils with specific locations in the catchment point to AG, CB and SS
435 sources as the most erodible areas. Thus, due to soil redistribution processes, these
436 sources show significant differences in the study properties. However, in the headwaters
437 the croplands recently abandoned due to more difficult access, which support less
438 intensive farming, show more similarities with OF. Furthermore, the higher connectivity
439 between OF that surrounds the AG areas in the headwaters further contributes to
440 similarities found in their soil properties. All these factors operating together in the
441 headwaters likely increase similarities between AG and OF as seen in the results of the
442 cluster analysis.

443 Exceptional rainfall events produce increases in connectivity and suspended
444 sediment loads and modify the channel bed sediments by decreasing or increasing the
445 concentration of different size particles during floods. The significant differences for most
446 study properties between pre- and post-event sediment point to exceptional storm events
447 as the main factors in causing sediment mobilisation from different sources, resulting in
448 subsequent variation of geochemistry and sediment properties as was also reported by

449 [Martins et al. \(1995\)](#). The sharp decrease experienced by the fine fraction and the increase
450 in the coarse fraction suggests that exceptional storm events export high quantities of
451 sediment composed mostly of fine sediment as was also found by [Bortoluzzi et al. \(2013\)](#)
452 in a Brazilian catchment. This hypothesis is supported by the decrease in most sediment
453 properties positively correlated with the clay fraction. However, the non-significant
454 differences in ^{137}Cs and magnetic properties could be explained by the large variability
455 of these properties across the catchment.

456 During heavy storm events, the sediment begins to be exported and reach a
457 maximum, beyond which the sediment exported begins to decline leading to an ordered
458 sedimentation and the increase of the mobilised element correlation ([Quesada et al., 2014](#);
459 [Gaspar et al., 2019b](#)) (Fig. 3). In our catchment, high sediment mobilisation is supported
460 by the increase in overall intercorrelation of the study elements that are correlated with
461 the grain size.

462 *4.2. Temporal and spatial variation of sediment mixture properties*

463 The variation of sediment properties in the stream channel before and after the
464 exceptional event as well as in the floodplains at an intermediate stage of sediment
465 deposited by regular high floods is related to the export of the fine grain size fractions.
466 Thus, the loss of fine material produces the subsequent enrichment in the content of coarse
467 fractions after rainfall events as was also found by [Smith and Olyphant \(1994\)](#) resulting
468 in the highest sand content in channel bed sediment after the exceptional rainfall event.

469 The elements positively correlated with argillaceous materials (i.e.,
470 aluminosilicates contained in the fine fraction such as ^{137}Cs , Rb, Sr, Fe, Zn, Al, Cr, Pb)
471 show a clear decreasing trend from pre-event, floodplain and post-event sediment due to
472 the reduction of fine materials that are exported during high floods. [Mitchell et al. \(1997\)](#)
473 and [Quiquerez et al. \(2008\)](#) also reported high export rates of fine sediment material and

474 associated nutrients. Thus, vanadium, which is finely incorporated into clay minerals
475 during weathering, is also exported. There are some elements such as Ba and Mn that
476 have limited mobility because they are easily precipitated as sulphates and carbonates.
477 Furthermore, Ba and Mn can also be strongly absorbed by clay minerals, which also
478 explains the slight decrease of Ba and Mn in floodplain and post-event sediment and
479 supports the hypothesis of high fine sediment export during storm events. On the other
480 hand, Si is directly correlated with the coarse fraction due to the high content of silicon
481 grains in the sandstone strata. Many Ti-containing minerals are resistant to weathering
482 (also Zr) and increase with the coarse fraction. Additionally, Nb exhibits a strong affinity
483 with Ti and Zr. All these mineral-element associations lead to increases of Ti, Zr, Nb and
484 Si after the storm event in parallel with the increase in the coarse fraction. Therefore, the
485 chemical changes observed are due to the mixing of soil sediment mobilised during the
486 exceptional event with pre-existing soil sediments mobilised during regular rainfalls.

487

488 *4.3. Sediment source contributions variation*

489 The contribution of channel bed changes before and after the event (but also from
490 headwaters to the lower part of the catchment) is due to the great modification power of
491 these exceptional storm events. In SMP 13 located in the headwaters, 30% of apportions
492 come from PI and SS sources, but during floods most of these sediments are exported,
493 and thus CB becomes the predominant source. Our results suggest that during the
494 exceptional event, most of the channel bed sediment is efficiently exported. PI sediment
495 was also exported in SMP 15 during the storm event; however, due to the proximity of
496 steep slopes (19 to 25°) with highly disturbed areas and the predominance of bare soils in
497 the contributing area, SS appears as the dominant source after the storm event.

498 Results obtained from both the floodplain sediment and the channel bed sediment
499 mixtures at SMP 15 where subsoil apportions are predominant suggest that during storm
500 events, sediment from surrounding slopes with highly degraded soils directly reaches the
501 stream. This interpretation is also supported by results at SMP 17 located in the middle
502 part of the catchment downstream from SMP 15 with a similarly high subsoil
503 contribution. The subsoil contribution then gradually decreases in the lower part of the
504 catchment (SMP 18 and 20) after the storm event. Such exceptional rainfalls produce
505 large variations on the sediment mobilised from different sources thus changing sediment
506 source contributions to the streams as can be seen in **Fig. 6.**

507 A different behaviour is observed in sediment mixtures located upstream from the La
508 Reina ephemeral stream and those located in the lower part of the catchment at SMP 18
509 and 20. At these points, the fingerprinting analysis shows a high increase of AG
510 provenance that is likely related to the incision of the main stream over the agricultural
511 land located on the glacia and the sediment apportion from the La Reina ephemeral
512 stream.

513 The deep incision of the streams and the almost vertical slopes of the channel
514 banks along with the nature of non-cohesive infilling material are the reason that CB is
515 the source that produces the highest sediment supply. The incision of the streams is highly
516 variable across the catchment, but overall, it increases downstream from the La Reina
517 ephemeral stream where the glacia starts. In addition, during heavy storms,
518 geomorphological processes such as piping, topples and landslides are likely to increase
519 apportionment from CB sources (Gaspar et al., 2019).

520 During heavy rainfalls, sediment resuspension due to energy expenditure in the
521 channel is higher in the headwaters and the middle part of the catchment (i.e., SMP 13,
522 SMP 15 and SMP 17) than in the lower part of the catchment. Sediment resuspension

523 could produce deposition downstream due to the loss of energy thus increasing the
524 sediment storage in the lower part of the catchment. This is similar, though on a different
525 scale, to what has been observed in the lower part of the Ebro River by [Quesada et al.](#)
526 [\(2014\)](#). The cluster analysis results also support the different functioning of the
527 headwaters and the lower part of the catchment. Furthermore, the results of the relative
528 source contribution (RSC) (Table 3) highlight the high sediment export from subsoil and
529 emphasise the low apportionments from natural covers such as OF. These results are in good
530 agreement with studies by [López-Tarazón et al. \(2009\)](#) and [Palazón et al. \(2016\)](#) and
531 further support the idea of bare soil as one of the main environmental problems for river
532 ecosystems.

533

534 **5. Conclusions**

535 Large changes in the characteristics of sediment were produced by an exceptional
536 storm event, modifying element concentrations and sediment provenance. The significant
537 differences between pre- and post-storm sediment mixtures highlight the great impact of
538 such storm events on channel bed sediment. Bearing in mind the observed spatial
539 variations in sediment properties and grain-size distributions, one may conclude that the
540 sediment mobilisation and transfer produced in the catchment was highly dynamic.

541 Placing the channel bed sediment apportionments in a geomorphological context,
542 our model results indicate an important input from SS despite its spatial coverage in the
543 catchment in amounts less than 2%. Therefore, the subsoil is suggested to be an important
544 environmental problem with hot spots that are worth controlling. In contrast, the
545 insignificant sediment apportionment from forests underlines the benefits of natural
546 covers to prevent soil loss.

547 Composite fingerprints provide the opportunity to efficiently trace sediment
548 sources before and after exceptional rainstorm events. Overall, our results provide
549 evidence of the severe erosion produced by this exceptional rainstorm event and reveal
550 important variations in sediment source patterns. Stream bank failure induced by natural
551 tunnelling or piping and landslides significantly contributed to sediment delivery. The
552 magnitude of agricultural and bare soil mobilisation during the course of this exceptional
553 rainstorm was much greater than under normal discharge regimes. Similar conclusions
554 are derived from the analysis of variations in sediment properties between pre-event SMP,
555 SMFP and post-event SMP. The geomorphological analysis, the fingerprinting procedure,
556 and the low RMSE obtained with virtual mixtures support the good performance of the
557 new FingerPro unmixing model to quantify the different sediment source apportionments.

558

559 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

560 This work has been supported by project CGL2014-52986-R funded by the
561 Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities and the aid of a predoctoral
562 contract (BES-2015-071780).

563

564 **REFERENCES**

565 Blake, W.H., Boeckx, P., Stock, B.C., Smith, H.G., Bodé, S., Upadhayay, H.R., Gaspar,
566 L., Goddard, R., Lennard, A.T., Lizaga, I., Lobb, D.A., Owens, P.N., Peticrew,
567 E.L., Kuzyk, Z.Z.A., Gari, B.D., Munishi, L., Mtei, K., Nebiyu, A., Mabit, L.,
568 Navas, A., Semmens, B.X., 2018. A deconvolutional Bayesian mixing model
569 approach for river basin sediment source apportionment. *Scientific Reports* 8,
570 13073. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-30905-9>

- 571 Bortoluzzi, E.C., dos Santos, D.R., Santanna, M.A., Caner, L., 2013. Mineralogy and
 572 nutrient desorption of suspended sediments during a storm event. *J Soils Sediments*
 573 13, 1093–1105. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-013-0692-4>
- 574 Borrelli, P., Robinson, D.A., Fleischer, L.R., Lugato, E., Ballabio, C., Alewell, C.,
 575 Meusburger, K., Modugno, S., Schütt, B., Ferro, V., Bagarello, V., Oost, K.V.,
 576 Montanarella, L., Panagos, P., 2017. An assessment of the global impact of 21st
 577 century land use change on soil erosion. *Nature Communications* 8, 2013.
 578 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02142-7>
- 579 Buendia, C., Batalla, R.J., Sabater, S., Palau, A., Marcé, R., 2016. Runoff Trends Driven
 580 by Climate and Afforestation in a Pyrenean Basin. *Land Degrad. Develop.* 27, 823–
 581 838. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2384>
- 582 Cavalli, M., Trevisani, S., Comiti, F., Marchi, L., 2013. Geomorphometric assessment of
 583 spatial sediment connectivity in small Alpine catchments. *Geomorphology,*
 584 *Sediment sources, source-to-sink fluxes and sedimentary budgets* 188, 31–41.
 585 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2012.05.007>
- 586 Chen, J., Shi, Z., Wen, A., Yan, D., Chen, T., 2019. ¹³⁷Cs-Based Variation of Soil
 587 Erosion in Vertical Zones of a Small Catchment in Southwestern China.
 588 *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16, 1371.
 589 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16081371>
- 590 Collins, A.L., Walling, D.E., 2002. Selecting fingerprint properties for discriminating
 591 potential suspended sediment sources in river basins. *Journal of Hydrology* 261,
 592 218–244. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(02\)00011-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(02)00011-2)
- 593 Collins, A., Walling, D., Leeks, G.J.L., 1996. Composite fingerprinting of the spatial
 594 source of fluvial suspended sediment : a case study of the Exe and Severn river

- 595 basins, United Kingdom. *Géomorphologie : relief, processus, environnement* 2, 41–
 596 53. <https://doi.org/10.3406/morfo.1996.877>
- 597 Collins, A.L., Walling, D.E., Leeks, G.J.L., 1997. Source type ascription for fluvial
 598 suspended sediment based on a quantitative composite fingerprinting technique.
 599 *CATENA* 29, 1–27. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0341-8162\(96\)00064-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0341-8162(96)00064-1)
- 600 Collins, A.L., Pulley, S., Foster, I.D.L., Gellis, A., Porto, P., Horowitz, A.J., 2017.
 601 Sediment source fingerprinting as an aid to catchment management: A review of
 602 the current state of knowledge and a methodological decision-tree for end-users.
 603 *Journal of Environmental Management*, Sediment source fingerprinting for
 604 informing catchment management: methodological approaches, problems and
 605 uncertainty 194, 86–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.09.075>
- 606 Dutta, S., 2016. Soil erosion, sediment yield and sedimentation of reservoir: a review.
 607 *Model. Earth Syst. Environ.* 2, 123. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-016-0182-y>
- 608 Evrard, O., Poulenard, J., Némery, J., Ayrault, S., Gratiot, N., Duvert, C., Prat, C.,
 609 Lefèvre, I., Bonté, P., Esteves, M., 2013. Tracing sediment sources in a tropical
 610 highland catchment of central Mexico by using conventional and alternative
 611 fingerprinting methods. *Hydrol. Process.* 27, 911–922.
 612 <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.9421>
- 613 Favis-Mortlock, D., 2008. Soil erosion and sediment redistribution in river catchments:
 614 Measurement, modelling and management, edited by P. N. Owens and A. J. Collins.
 615 CABI, Wallingford, UK, 2006. ISBN 978 0 85199 050 7, xiv+328 pp. *Land*
 616 *Degradation & Development* 19, 694–694. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.872>
- 617 García-Ruiz, J.M., Martí-Bono, C., Lorente, A., Beguería, S., 2002. Geomorphological
 618 consequences of frequent and infrequent rainfall and hydrological events in

- 619 Pyrennez Mountains of Spain. Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global
 620 Change 7, 303–320. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1024479630433>
- 621 Gaspar, L., Navas, A., Walling, D.E., Machín, J., Gómez Arozamena, J., 2013. Using
 622 ^{137}Cs and $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ to assess soil redistribution on slopes at different temporal scales.
 623 Catena, Scales in Soil Erosion 102, 46–54.
 624 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2011.01.004>
- 625 Gaspar, L., Blake, W.H., Smith, H.G., Lizaga, I., Navas, A., 2019a. Testing the sensitivity
 626 of a multivariate mixing model using geochemical fingerprints with artificial
 627 mixtures. Geoderma 337, 498–510.
 628 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.10.005>
- 629 Gaspar, L., Lizaga, I., Blake, W.H., Latorre, B., Quijano, L., Navas, A. 2019b.
 630 Fingerprinting changes in source contribution for evaluating soil response during
 631 an exceptional rainfall in Spanish Pre-Pyrenees. Journal of Environmental
 632 Management, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.03.109>
- 633 Grodek, T., Jacoby, Y., Morin, E., Katz, O., 2012. Effectiveness of exceptional rainstorms
 634 on a small Mediterranean basin. Geomorphology 159–160, 156–168.
 635 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2012.03.016>
- 636 Gutiérrez, F., Gutiérrez, M., Sancho, C., 1998. Geomorphological and sedimentological
 637 analysis of a catastrophic flash flood in the Arás drainage basin (Central Pyrenees,
 638 Spain). Geomorphology 22, 265–283. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X(97)00087-1)
 639 [555X\(97\)00087-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X(97)00087-1)
- 640 Heckmann, T., Cavalli, M., Cerdan, O., Foerster, S., Javaux, M., Lode, E., Smetanová,
 641 A., Vericat, D., Brardinoni, F., 2018. Indices of sediment connectivity:
 642 opportunities, challenges and limitations. Earth-Science Reviews 187, 77–108.
 643 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2018.08.004>

- 644 Klages, M.G., Hsieh, Y.P., 1975. Suspended Solids Carried by the Gallatin River of
 645 Southwestern Montana: II. Using Mineralogy for Inferring Sources. *Journal of*
 646 *Environmental Quality* 4, 68–73.
 647 <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq1975.00472425000400010016x>
- 648 Koiter, A.J., Owens, P.N., Petticrew, E.L., Lobb, D.A., 2013. The behavioural
 649 characteristics of sediment properties and their implications for sediment
 650 fingerprinting as an approach for identifying sediment sources in river basins.
 651 *Earth-Science Reviews* 125, 24–42.
 652 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2013.05.009>
- 653 Koiter, A.J., Owens, P.N., Petticrew, E.L., Lobb, D.A., 2018. Assessment of particle size
 654 and organic matter correction factors in sediment source fingerprinting
 655 investigations: An example of two contrasting watersheds in Canada. *Geoderma*
 656 325, 195–207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.02.044>
- 657 Lana-Renault, N., Nadal-Romero, E., Serrano-Muela, M.P., Alvera, B., Sánchez-
 658 Navarrete, P., Sanjuan, Y., García-Ruiz, J.M., 2013. Comparative analysis of the
 659 response of various land covers to an exceptional rainfall event in the central
 660 Spanish Pyrenees, October 2012. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 39, 581–
 661 592. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3465>
- 662 Lasanta, T., Nadal-Romero, E., Errea, P., Arnáez, J., 2016. The Effect of Landscape
 663 Conservation Measures in Changing Landscape Patterns: A Case Study in
 664 Mediterranean Mountains. *Land Degrad. Develop.* 27, 373–386.
 665 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2359>
- 666 Lecce, S.A., 2013. Stream power, channel change, and channel geometry in the Blue
 667 River, Wisconsin. *Physical Geography* 34, 293–314.
 668 <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723646.2013.847311>

- 669 Li, M., Yao, W., Ding, W., Yang, J., Chen, J., 2009. Effect of grass coverage on sediment
 670 yield in the hillslope-gully side erosion system. *J. Geogr. Sci.* 19, 321–330.
 671 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11442-009-0321-8>
- 672 Lizaga, I., Quijano, L., Palazón, L., Gaspar, L., Navas, A., 2017. Enhancing Connectivity
 673 Index to Assess the Effects of Land Use Changes in a Mediterranean Catchment.
 674 *Land Degrad. Develop.* 663–675. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2676>
- 675 Lizaga, I., Quijano, L., Gaspar, L., Navas, A., 2018a. Estimating Soil Redistribution
 676 Patterns with ¹³⁷Cs Measurements in a Mediterranean Mountain Catchment
 677 Affected by Land Abandonment. *Land Degrad. Develop.* 105–117.
 678 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2843>
- 679 Lizaga, I., Latorre, B., Gaspar, L., Navas, A., 2018b. fingerPro: an R Package for
 680 Sediment Source Tracing. [https://cran.r-](https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/fingerPro/index.html)
 681 [project.org/web/packages/fingerPro/index.html](https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/fingerPro/index.html).
 682 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1402029>
- 683 Lizaga, I., Quijano, L., Gaspar, L., Ramos, M.C., Navas, A., 2019. Linking land use
 684 changes to variation in soil properties in a Mediterranean mountain agroecosystem.
 685 *Catena* 172, 516–527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2018.09.019>
- 686 Llana, M., Vericat, D., Cavalli, M., Crema, S., Smith, M.W., 2019. The effects of land
 687 use and topographic changes on sediment connectivity in mountain catchments.
 688 *Science of The Total Environment* 660, 899–912.
 689 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.12.479>
- 690 López-Tarazón, J.A., Batalla, R.J., Vericat, D., Francke, T., 2009. Suspended sediment
 691 transport in a highly erodible catchment: The River Isábena (Southern Pyrenees).
 692 *Geomorphology* 109, 210–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2009.03.003>

- 693 Mabit, L., Bernard, C., Laverdiere, M.R., 2002. Quantification of soil redistribution and
694 sediment budget in a Canadian watershed from fallout caesium-137 (¹³⁷Cs) data.
695 Canadian journal of soil science.
- 696 Mariani, L., Parisi, S.G., 2014. Exceptional Rainfalls in the Mediterranean Area, in:
697 Storminess and Environmental Change, Advances in Natural and Technological
698 Hazards Research. Springer, Dordrecht, pp. 17–37. [https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-7948-8_2)
699 [007-7948-8_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-7948-8_2)
- 700 Martínez-Carreras, N., Krein, A., Udelhoven, T., Gallart, F., Iffly, J.F., Hoffmann, L.,
701 Pfister, L., Walling, D.E., 2010. A rapid spectral-reflectance-based fingerprinting
702 approach for documenting suspended sediment sources during storm runoff events.
703 J Soils Sediments 10, 400–413. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-009-0162-1>
- 704 Martins, A.A.A., Madeira, M.V., Refega, A.A.G., 1995. Influence of rainfall on
705 properties of soils developed on granite in Portugal. Arid Soil Research and
706 Rehabilitation 9, 353–366. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15324989509385904>
- 707 Masselink, R.H., Temme, A.J. a. M., Giménez Díaz, R., Casalí Sarasíbar, J., Keesstra,
708 S.D., 2017. Assessing hillslope-channel connectivity in an agricultural catchment
709 using rare-earth oxide tracers and random forests models.
710 <https://doi.org/10.18172/cig.3169>
- 711 Meusburger, K., Porto, P., Mabit, L., La Spada, C., Arata, L., Alewell, C., 2018. Excess
712 Lead-210 and Plutonium-239+240: Two suitable radiogenic soil erosion tracers for
713 mountain grassland sites. Environmental Research 160, 195–202.
714 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.09.020>
- 715 Mitchell, A.W., Bramley, R.G.V., Johnson, A.K.L., 1997. Export of nutrients and
716 suspended sediment during a cyclone-mediated flood event in the Herbert River

- 717 catchment, Australia. Mar. Freshwater Res. 48, 79–88.
 718 <https://doi.org/10.1071/mf96021>
- 719 Moore, J.W., Semmens, B.X., 2008. Incorporating uncertainty and prior information into
 720 stable isotope mixing models. Ecology Letters 11, 470–480.
 721 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2008.01163.x>
- 722 Nadal-Romero, E., Martínez, T.L., González-Hidalgo, J.C., Luis, M. de, García-Ruiz,
 723 J.M., 2013. The effect of intense rainstorm events on the suspended sediment
 724 response under various land uses : the Aísa Valley experimental station. Cuadernos
 725 de Investigación Geográfica 38, 27–47. <https://doi.org/10.18172/cig.1274>
- 726 Nadal-Romero, E., Khorchani, M., Lasanta, T., García-Ruiz, J.M., 2019. Runoff and
 727 Solute Outputs under Different Land Uses: Long-Term Results from a
 728 Mediterranean Mountain Experimental Station. Water 11, 976.
 729 <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11050976>
- 730 Navas, A., Valero-Garcés, B.L., Machín, J. 2004. An approach to integrated assesment
 731 of reservoir siltation: the Joaquín Costa reservoir as case study. Hydrology and
 732 Earth System Sciences, 8 (6): 1193-1199.
- 733 Navas, A., Machín, J., Soto, J. 2005. Assessing soil erosion in a Pyrenean mountain
 734 catchment using GIS and fallout ¹³⁷Cs. Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment,
 735 105: 493-506.
- 736 Navas, A., Machín, J., Beguería, S., López-Vicente, M., Gaspar. L. 2008. Soil properties
 737 and physiographic factors controlling the natural vegetation re-growth in a
 738 disturbed catchment of the Central Spanish Pyrenees. Agroforestry Systems, 72(3):
 739 173-185.

- 740 Navas, A., Valero-Garcés, B.L, Gaspar, L., Machín, J. 2009. Reconstructing the history
741 of sediment accumulation in the Yesa reservoir: an approach for management of
742 mountain reservoirs. *Lake and Reservoir Management*, 25 (1): 15-27.
- 743 Navas, A., López-Vicente, M., Gaspar, L., Machín, J., 2013. Assessing soil redistribution
744 in a complex karst catchment using fallout ¹³⁷Cs and GIS. *Geomorphology*,
745 *Geomorphology in Spain Special issue in honour of Prof. Mateo Gutiérrez* 196,
746 231–241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2012.03.018>
- 747 Navas, A., López-Vicente, M., Gaspar, L., Palazón, L., Quijano, L., 2014. Establishing a
748 tracer-based sediment budget to preserve wetlands in Mediterranean mountain
749 agroecosystems (NE Spain). *Science of The Total Environment* 496, 132–143.
750 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.07.026>
- 751 Navas, A., Quine, T.A., Walling, D.E., Gaspar, L., Quijano, L., Lizaga, I., 2017. Relating
752 intensity of soil redistribution to land use changes in abandoned Pyrenean fields
753 using fallout caesium-137. *Land Degrad. Develop.* n/a-n/a.
754 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2724>
- 755 Navas, A., Serrano, E., López-Martínez, J., Gaspar, L., Lizaga, I. 2018. Interpreting
756 environmental changes from radionuclides and soil characteristics in different
757 landform contexts of Elephant Island (Maritime Antarctica). *Land Degradation and*
758 *Development*, 29: 3141-3158. DOI: 10.1002/ldr.2987
- 759 Owens, P.N., Blake, W.H., Gaspar, L., Gateuille, D., Koiter, A.J., Lobb, D.A., Petticrew,
760 E.L., Reiffarth, D.G., Smith, H.G., Woodward, J.C., 2016. Fingerprinting and
761 tracing the sources of soils and sediments: Earth and ocean science,
762 geoarchaeological, forensic, and human health applications. *Earth-Science Reviews*
763 162, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2016.08.012>

- 764 Palazón, L., Gaspar, L., Latorre, B., Blake, W.H., Navas, A., 2015a. Identifying sediment
 765 sources by applying a fingerprinting mixing model in a Pyrenean drainage
 766 catchment. *J Soils Sediments* 15, 2067–2085. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-015-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-015-1175-6)
 767 1175-6
- 768 Palazón, L., Latorre, B., Gaspar, L., Blake, W.H., Smith, H.G., Navas, A., 2015b.
 769 Comparing catchment sediment fingerprinting procedures using an auto-evaluation
 770 approach with virtual sample mixtures. *Science of The Total Environment* 532,
 771 456–466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.05.003>
- 772 Palazón, L., Latorre B., Leticia Gaspar, G., Blake, W.H., Smith, H.G., Navas, A. 2016.
 773 Combining catchment modelling and sediment fingerprinting to assess sediment
 774 dynamics in a Spanish Pyrenean river system. **Science of the Total Environment**
 775 569–570: 1136–1148.doi: [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.06.189](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.06.189)
- 776 Phillips, D.L., Gregg, J.W., 2003. Source partitioning using stable isotopes: coping with
 777 too many sources. *Oecologia* 136, 261–269. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-003-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-003-1218-3)
 778 1218-3
- 779 Pimentel, D., 2006. Soil Erosion: A Food and Environmental Threat. *Environ Dev Sustain*
 780 8, 119–137. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-005-1262-8>
- 781 Porto, P., Walling, D.E., Ferro, V., di Stefano, C., 2003. Validating erosion rate estimates
 782 provided by caesium-137 measurements for two small forested catchments in
 783 Calabria, southern Italy. *Land Degrad. Dev.* 14, 389–408.
 784 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.561>
- 785 Pulley, S., Foster, I., Antunes, P., 2015. The uncertainties associated with sediment
 786 fingerprinting suspended and recently deposited fluvial sediment in the Nene river
 787 basin. *Geomorphology* 228, 303–319.

- 788 Pulley, S., Collins, A.L., 2018. Tracing catchment fine sediment sources using the new
 789 SIFT (Sediment Fingerprinting Tool) open source software. *Science of The Total*
 790 *Environment* 635, 838–858. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.126>
- 791 Quesada, S., Tena, A., Guillén, D., Ginebreda, A., Vericat, D., Martínez, E., Navarro-
 792 Ortega, A., Batalla, R.J., Barceló, D., 2014. Dynamics of suspended sediment borne
 793 persistent organic pollutants in a large regulated Mediterranean river (Ebro, NE
 794 Spain). *Science of The Total Environment* 473–474, 381–390.
 795 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.11.040>
- 796 Quijano, L., Gaspar, L., Navas, A., 2016a. Spatial patterns of SOC, SON, ¹³⁷Cs and soil
 797 properties as affected by redistribution processes in a Mediterranean cultivated field
 798 (Central Ebro Basin). *Soil and Tillage Research* 155, 318–328.
 799 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2015.09.007>
- 800 Quijano, L., Beguería, S., Gaspar, L., Navas, A., 2016b. Estimating erosion rates using
 801 ¹³⁷Cs measurements and WATEM/SEDEM in a Mediterranean cultivated field.
 802 *CATENA* 138, 38–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2015.11.009>
- 803 Quiquerez, A., Brenot, J., Garcia, J.-P., Petit, C., 2008. Soil degradation caused by a high-
 804 intensity rainfall event: Implications for medium-term soil sustainability in
 805 Burgundian vineyards. *CATENA* 73, 89–97.
 806 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2007.09.007>
- 807 Renard, K.G., Yoder, D.C., Lightle, D.T., Dabney, S.M., 2011. Universal Soil Loss
 808 Equation and Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation, in: *Handbook of Erosion*
 809 *Modelling*. Wiley-Blackwell, pp. 135–167.
 810 <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444328455.ch8>

- 811 Romanyà, J., Rovira, P., 2011. An appraisal of soil organic C content in Mediterranean
 812 agricultural soils. *Soil Use and Management* 27, 321–332.
 813 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-2743.2011.00346.x>
- 814 Schuller, P., Walling, D.E., Iroumé, A., Quilodrán, C., Castillo, A., Navas, A. 2013.
 815 Using ^{137}Cs and $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ and other sediment source fingerprints to document
 816 suspended sediment sources in small forested catchments in south-central Chile.
 817 *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity*, 124: 147-159. [doi:](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2013.05.002)
 818 [10.1016/j.jenvrad.2013.05.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2013.05.002)
- 819 Serrano-Muela, M.P., Nadal-Romero, E., Lana-Renault, N., González-Hidalgo, J.C.,
 820 López-Moreno, J.I., Beguería, S., Sanjuan, Y., García-Ruiz, J.M., 2015. An
 821 exceptional rainfall event in the central western Pyrenees: spatial patterns in
 822 discharge and impact. *Land Degradation & Development* 26, 249–262.
- 823 Serrano-Notivoli, R., Mora, D., Ollero, A., Sánchez-Fabre, M., Sanz, P., Saz, M.Á., 2017.
 824 Floodplain occupation and flooding in the Central Pyrenees. *Cuadernos de*
 825 *Investigación Geográfica* 43, 309–328. <https://doi.org/10.18172/cig.3057>
- 826 Shang, Z.H., Cao, J.J., Degen, A.A., Zhang, D.W., Long, R.J., 2019. A four year study in
 827 a desert land area on the effect of irrigated, cultivated land and abandoned cropland
 828 on soil biological, chemical and physical properties. *CATENA* 175, 1–8.
 829 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2018.12.002>
- 830 Smith, L.C., Olyphant, G.A., 1994. Within-storm variations in runoff and sediment export
 831 from a rapidly eroding coal-refuse deposit. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*
 832 19, 369–375. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3290190407>
- 833 Smith, H.G., Blake, W.H., 2014. Sediment fingerprinting in agricultural catchments: A
 834 critical re-examination of source discrimination and data corrections.
 835 *Geomorphology* 204, 177–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2013.08.003>

- 836 Upadhayay, H.R., Smith, H.G., Griepentrog, M., Bodé, S., Bajracharya, R.M., Blake, W.,
837 Cornelis, W., Boeckx, P., 2018. Community managed forests dominate the
838 catchment sediment cascade in the mid-hills of Nepal: A compound-specific stable
839 isotope analysis. *Science of The Total Environment* 637–638, 306–317.
840 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.394>
- 841 Verheijen, F.G.A., Jones, R.J.A., Rickson, R.J., Smith, C.J., 2009. Tolerable versus actual
842 soil erosion rates in Europe. *Earth-Science Reviews* 94, 23–38.
843 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2009.02.003>
- 844 Walling, D.E., 2005. Tracing suspended sediment sources in catchments and river
845 systems. *Science of The Total Environment* 344, 159–184.
846 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2005.02.011>
- 847 Walling, D.E., Collins, A.L., 2008. The catchment sediment budget as a management
848 tool. *Environmental Science & Policy, Monitoring and modelling diffuse pollution*
849 *from agriculture for policy support: UK and European experience.* 11, 136–143.
850 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2007.10.004>
- 851 Walling, D.E., Peart, M.R., Oldfield, F., Thompson, R., 1979. Suspended sediment
852 sources identified by magnetic measurements. *Nature* 281, 281110a0.
853 <https://doi.org/10.1038/281110a0>
- 854 Walling, D.E., Woodward, J.C., 1995. Tracing sources of suspended sediment in river
855 basins: a case study of the River Culm, Devon, UK. *Marine and Freshwater*
856 *Research* 46, 327–336.
- 857 White, S., García-Ruiz, J.M., Martí, C., Valero, B., Errea, M.P., Gómez-Villar, A., 1997.
858 The 1996 Biescas campsite disaster in the Central Spanish Pyrenees, and its
859 temporal and spatial context. *Hydrological Processes* 11, 1797–1812.

- 860 [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1085\(199711\)11:14<1797::AID-](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1085(199711)11:14<1797::AID-)
861 [HYP605>3.0.CO;2-7](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1085(199711)11:14<1797::AID-HYP605>3.0.CO;2-7)
- 862 Winston, W.E., Criss, R.E., 2002. Geochemical variations during flash flooding,
863 Meramec River basin, May 2000. *Journal of Hydrology* 265, 149–163.
864 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(02\)00105-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(02)00105-1)
- 865 Wynants, M., Solomon, H., Ndakidemi, P., Blake, W.H., 2018. Pinpointing areas of
866 increased soil erosion risk following land cover change in the Lake Manyara
867 catchment, Tanzania. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and*
868 *Geoinformation* 71, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2018.05.008>
- 869 Yu, L., Oldfield, F., 1989. A multivariate mixing model for identifying sediment source
870 from magnetic measurements. *Quaternary Research* 32, 168–181.
871 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(89\)90073-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(89)90073-2)
- 872 Zhang, J., Yang, M., Zhang, F., Zhang, W., Zhao, T., Li, Y., 2017. Fingerprinting
873 Sediment Sources After an Exceptional Rainstorm Event in a Small Catchment on
874 the Loess Plateau, PR China. *Land Degradation & Development* 28, 2527–2539.
875 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2803>
- 876
877
878
879
880
881
882
883
884

885 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

886 Fig. 1. Location of the study catchment in the central part of the Ebro Basin (NE Spain).
887 3D map of the different land uses in the catchment with the sources and mixture sampling
888 point distribution through the catchment. (a) Pine afforestation, (b) subsoil, (c) open forest
889 and (d) agricultural.

890

891 Fig. 2. Boxplots of pre- and post-storm sediment properties. Asterisks represent the
892 elements that are significantly different between stages.

893

894 Fig. 3. Correlation coefficients of the different sediment properties before and after the
895 exceptional storm event.

896

897 Fig. 4. Linear discrimination analysis (LDA) plot of the different sources in the Barués
898 catchment. (13–20) Cluster analysis of the different sources presented in the mixture
899 points. The darker colours show a stronger correlation while the brighter colours show
900 a lower correlation.

901

902 Fig. 5. Bar plot of sediment properties for the three different flood stages: pre-event,
903 regular flood and post-event.

904

905 Fig. 6. Results of the unmixing procedure before and after the exceptional storm event in
906 each mixture point. An ANOVA test was performed to assess whether source contribution
907 differed between pre- and post-event mixtures. Different letters indicate significant
908 differences at the 95% level.